

LATER PATTERNS AND ISSUES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract:

This article briefly discusses the latest trends in English language teaching and learning. Also, guidelines for teaching dialects, which have become a worldwide challenge for teaching English to 21st century learners, will be revised.

Key words: effective, engagement, culture, curriculum subjects, performance, meaningful, results, learner-centered, collaborative, and technology-oriented

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/dc0z4c47>

English language teaching has been used for decades. The ELT trend that was widely used by educators in the past has disappeared and been replaced by other trends today. This is why language teaching in the 20th century underwent many changes and innovations. Teachers must understand students' needs and barriers to effectively engage them in English language learning. Investigate current ELL concerns and trends, including student engagement, culture, and core curriculum.

Problem with the Core Curriculum

"English language learners may be academically behind their peers," said Patricia, an English as a Second Language teaching candidate. This is due in part to the fact that English language training in general does not focus on key curricular areas such as math, reading, and science. If a student is attempting to learn fundamental English while also learning the particular language related with core curriculum areas, the learner may become overwhelmed. As a result, a new trend in English language education is for teachers to become more actively involved in mentoring students not only in English but also in the context of the core curriculum." While research into the matter is underway, officials in charge of modifying educational regulations are considering including ESL classes into the basic curriculum. Academic achievement of pupils in the core curriculum, for example, is used to evaluate public schools.

Patricia, an American and normal English speaker, says that the most entrancing study hall discussions spin around American culture, like food, occasions, and music. Patricia is right since showing language culture is one of the issues that influences the calling of English language instruction. Subsequently, there is a propensity among EFL educators to encourage them to show culture, which might push policymakers to integrate intercultural skill as a quality teacher trait.

That's what defenders guarantee assuming that understudies are taken part in the way of life, it is easier and more pleasurable to become familiar with

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International Conference

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a language. The language classroom of today is vastly different from the language classroom of the mid to late twentieth century. The emphasis is no longer on grammar, memorization, and note-taking, but on the application of language and cultural understanding in global communication. As children learn to engage with the world around them, utilizing their linguistic and cultural abilities to promote relationships, technology transcends geographic and physical borders.

In conclusion, it is reasonable to reimagine a field that is more learner-centered, collaborative, and technologically driven. Language education trends propel us forward so that our students may communicate with people all around the world in real time.

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